

A forgotten letter from Roentgen.

A discharge tube designed by Prof. Roentgen and the Lenard issue

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Abstract:

While studying the circumstances under which Roentgen made his discovery in 1895, we came across a forgotten letter that sheds new light on a tube Roentgen may have used in his discovery. Roentgen probably also used this tube for the demonstration to the emperor.

Keywords:

History, Geissler, Roentgen, x ray tubes, Plücker, Crookes, cathode rays, Philipp Lenard, Emil Warburg, Otto Warburg, Müller-Unkel, Zehnder, Hittorf, Krebs, Meyer-Viol

Introduction

It is not known which discharge tube Roentgen (1845-1923) used for the discovery of x-rays, for which he won the first Nobel Prize for Physics in 1901. Roentgen worked with several types of tubes and consumed dozens.

There is a controversy surrounding the claim of Philipp Lenard (1862-1947). This German physicist (who won a Nobel Prize for Physics in 1905) claimed that Roentgen used his tube for the discovery, and was offended at never receiving an acknowledgement for this.[1] Remarkably, Roentgen never offered details on the tubes used in his first publication. The paper only states a list of tubes that can be used: *“a discharge from a large induction coil is passed through a Hittorf’s vacuum tube, or through a well-exhausted Lenard’s or Crookes’ tube, or similar devices”*.[2]

While studying the circumstances under which Roentgen made his discovery in 1895, we came across a forgotten letter that sheds new light on a tube that Roentgen may have used in his discovery.[3] And also on the extent to which Roentgen was indebted to Lenard's tube for his discovery.

The letter was written to his colleague, the well-known physicist Emil Warburg (1846-1931). How does this letter shed light on the controversy surrounding the type of tube used by Roentgen in his discovery of X-rays? This will be set out in this paper.

Discharge tubes

A discharge tube is a glass tube, which is partly evacuated and through which an electric current is passed with the help of electrodes melted into the glass wall. A systematic investigation of these discharges began in 1857 through the work of Heinrich Geissler (1814-1879).[4] This glassblower and instrument maker developed a technique to properly evacuate the tubes. He was able to enthruse the mathematician and physicist Julius Plücker (1801-1868) from Bonn for this research. This investigation of the light phenomena that occur in these tubes ultimately led to the discovery of the X-rays in 1895.

Johann Wilhelm Hittorf (1824-1914), student and colleague of Plücker, expanded the research, developed his own tubes and used a very efficient induction coil, the Ruhmkorff

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coil. He observed a dark region near one of the electrodes of the electric discharge. This region was named after him. About the same time, the same observation was made by Sir William Crookes (1832-1919) in England, where they speak of Crookes' dark space. All these tubes vary in size and shape, from cylinders to balloons and combinations of them, and the eponyms are often used interchangeably.

By lowering the pressure in the tube, the dark space widens and at a pressure of about 0,01 mm Hg it fills the whole tube.[5] Then the whole glass tube glows with a faint greenish light, produced by invisible rays emanating from the cathode itself: cathode rays. These cathode rays were extensively investigated by Hittorf and Crookes, and many others including Heinrich Hertz (1857-1894) and his assistant Lenard. Hertz had shown that cathode rays pass through a very thin foil of aluminium. Based on this finding, Lenard devised a tube with a thin aluminium foil window to bring the cathode rays outside the tube. This became known as the Lenard's tube. He describes this tube and his findings in a famous article of 1894.[6] Commissioned by Lenard, a variant of this tube, equipped with a small platinum tube on the frontside (fig. 1), was made by the glassblower Louis Müller-Unkel (1853-1938) from Braunschweig, Germany.

Figure 1 Müller-Unkel's "window tube" (Fensterröhre) with the little platina tube on the frontside left. (from Dörfel, G., 2010)

In the spring of 1894, after reading Lenard's article, Roentgen ordered such a tube from Müller-Unkel and he was excited about it, as he wrote to his friend and colleague Zehnder (1854-1949).[7] This was a year before his great discovery. Müller-Unkel was Roentgen's supplier of tubes during this time.[8]

As was mentioned above, Roentgen never explicitly stated which tube he was using at the time of his discovery of the X-rays. But we'll try to piece together the available evidence to figure out which tube he probably used.

Demonstration of X-rays to Emperor Wilhelm II

Shortly after the publication of his discovery, on 9 January 1896 Roentgen received a telegram from the German Emperor Wilhelm II with the following message:

“Wenn sich der Bericht bewahrheitet, so gratuliere ich Ihnen aus vollem Herzen und preise Gott, dass unserem deutschen Vaterlande der neue Triumph der Wissenschaft beschert ist, welcher hoffentlich von reichem Segen für die Menschheit sein wird. Sobald Sie Zeit haben, wäre ich Ihnen dankbar, wenn Sie mir einen Vortrag über Ihre Erfindung halten könnten. —Wilhelm, 1.R.”.[9]

“If the report is true, I congratulate you wholeheartedly and praise God that our German fatherland has been given the new triumph of science, which will hopefully be a blessing for mankind. As soon as you have time, I would be grateful if you could give me a lecture on your invention. —Wilhelm, i.R”.*(translation by author)*

A day later the Emperor's aide Von Arnim telegraphed to Roentgen that the emperor would like to accept the offer of a lecture by Roentgen on the 12th of January, at 5 o'clock in the afternoon. Von Arnim recommended that Roentgen should get in touch with the Berlin University if he needed a laboratory for his demonstration.[9]

Roentgen felt honored. He had not yet demonstrated his discovery in public. The next day, January 11, he went to Berlin with his assistant Stern. That same day, they made preparations for the demonstration in the laboratory of Emil Warburg, professor of experimental physics at the University of Berlin. The lecture for the emperor took place on the afternoon of January 12 in the “Sternensaal” of the Royal Palace in the presence of relatives of the emperor and several dignitaries.

The meeting was described in a letter to the newspaper Kölnische Zeitung:[10]

The professor first explained the nature of the Geissler tubes, then discussed the Hittorf experiments, went on to explain the cathode rays and finally came to the Crookes tubes. He supported his lecture with practical demonstrations by showing the phenomena caused by the electric current in the aforementioned devices [...] Finally, the professor demonstrated another Crookes tube, **the one he had brought with him, the only one he had left** (acc by author). Due to lack of time, he had been unable to acquire new tubes, and it is well known that the evacuation of such tubes takes four days, because it can only be done with the mercury air pump. The tube, which was enclosed in a cardboard wrapping, was connected to the electricity current [...] in the darkened room the fluorescence of the plate soaked in saline, brought near the tube, was clearly visible. This ended the lecture, and lively discussion followed. *(translation by author)*

This newspaper article lists three types of discharge tubes that were present at the meeting: Geissler, Crookes, and Hittorf tubes. These tubes must have come from Warburg's laboratory, as there was only one tube left of Roentgen himself. This is confirmed in a letter from Roentgen to his supplier Müller-Unkel, dated January 6, 1896:

Fast alle Apparate, die Sie mir schickten, sind aufgebraucht; aber ich habe auch was Hübsches damit erreicht. Nun gilt es auszuputzen, und neue zu bestellen.[8]

Almost all the devices you sent me have been used up; but then I've also achieved something nice with it. Now it's time to clean up and order new ones.
(translation by author)

In the same letter he places an order for two new specifically prescribed Hittorf tubes. He had no suitable tubes anymore and wanted to continue his research after the arduous period around his sensational publication. But he urgently needs another tube, even more than the other ones:

Dann schicken Sie mir noch einen Apparat nach beiliegender Skizze, der sich nur wenig von den früheren unterscheidet. Schicken Sie mir diese Röhre möglichst bald und warten Sie bei der Fertigstellung der Vacuumröhren.[8]

Then send me another device according to the attached sketch, which differs only slightly from the earlier ones. Send me this tube as soon as possible and wait with the completion of the vacuum tubes. (*translation by author*)

The sketch of this tube mentioned is unfortunately not available. It is possible, but unlikely, that the tube had already arrived before Roentgen headed for Berlin. The other tubes were certainly delivered later. The Geissler, Crookes and Hittorf tubes, most likely from the laboratory of Warburg, served to show the already well-known phenomena (color patterns, dark space of Crookes, cathode rays) that occur during the flow of electricity. A university physics laboratory at the time would have had these tubes available for education. But the tube with which he showed the x rays was most likely the tube he brought with him. What kind of tube was that?

The letter

One of the two letters, written by Roentgen to Warburg, published in 1973 by Hans Krebs, appears to shed a new light on this matter.[3]

Krebs (1900-1981), known for the Krebs cycle, had received the Nobel Prize in Physiology and Medicine in 1953 and was in the process of obtaining information about his colleague and Nobel Prize winner (1931) in the same field, the recently deceased Otto Warburg (1883-1970), son of Emil. He got in touch with Emil Warburg's grandson, Dr. Peter G. Meyer-Viol (1924-2009) from Maastricht (Netherlands). This grandson was in possession of these letters.ⁱ

The letter in question is one from Roentgen to Warburg, dated January 28, 1896. It was written in response to a letter from Warburg asking for information about Roentgen's curriculum vitae in connection with his nomination as corresponding member of the Berliner Akademie der Wissenschaften (Academy of Sciences). In addition to providing this information, Roentgen thanks Warburg for his help with the demonstration in the Royal Palace. He writes:

Ich möchte Ihnen nämlich nochmals herzlich danken für die grosse Bereitwilligkeit und Liebenswürdigkeit, die Sie mir in Berlin haben zu Theil werden lassen. Dass es mir überhaupt noch gelungen ist, dem Kaiser einige Versuchen zu machen, habe ich nur Ihnen aufopfernden Hilfe zu Verdanken, ohne diese wäre die Sache ziemlich "klaterig" ausgefallen.

It is to thank you again most warmly for great readiness and kindness which you have shown to me in Berlin. That I succeeded in doing some experiments for the

Kaiser was entirely due to your unfailing help without which the matter would have been rather a poor show. (*translation by Krebs*)

These words of thanks may indicate that Warburg indeed provided the aforementioned tubes. But which tube did Roentgen bring from home? It could be that he is referring to this tube in the continuation of the letter:

Die Ihnen empfohlenen Röhren haben sich sehr gut bewährt, wenn man die der Kathode gegenüberliegende Glaskuppe mit einem kleinen Zückchen Aluminiumfolie beklebt, das mit der Anode leitend verbunden wird. Die nöthige Verdünnung hält sich auch bei diesen Röhren erst dann durch ein etwas längere Zeit, wenn man die Röhren einige Tage von Zeit zu Teit zu Entladungen benutzt und gleich nachher wieder durch ein paar Pumpenschläge evacuirt.

The tubes recommended to you have been working very well, provided a small piece of aluminium foil is stuck to the glass cap opposite the cathode and is connected with a lead to the anode. The necessary evacuation keeps in these tubes for a longer period but only if, for some days, one makes the tubes discharge from time to time and immediately afterwards evacuates them again, with a few strokes of the pump. (*translation by Krebs*)

Roentgen here accentuated the need to keep the evacuation under control. The same month, he also pointed out the importance of sustained evacuation in a letter to Zehnder:

Ich gebrauche einen grossen Ruhmkorff, 50/20 cm, mit Deprezunterbrecher und ca. 20 A Primärstrom. Mein Apparat, der an der Rapschen Pumpe sitzen bleibt, braucht einige Tage zum Auspumpen: beste Wirkung, wenn die Funkenstrecke eines parallel geschalteten Entladlers ca. 3 cm beträgt.[7]

I use a large Ruhmkorff, 50/20 cm, with Deprezinterrupter and about 20 A primary current. My discharge tube, which remains attached to the Raps pump, takes a few days to pump out: best effect if the spark gap of the inductor is approx. 3 cm. (*translation by author*)

Vacuum tubes such as those from Hittorf and Crookes were manufactured with partial vacuum. In his letter of 6 January to Müller-Unkel, the firm providing him with discharge tubes, Roentgen complains about the breakdown of his vacuum tubes. Some tubes also develop longitudinal capillaries in the glass, which disrupt their function. It is understandable that he wanted to be on the safe side while giving his demonstration to the emperor. He started the demonstration by saying: "I hope that I have 'Kaiser Glück' (Emperor's luck), with this tube today, for these tubes are extremely sensitive and often destroyed in the very first experiment, and it takes me about four days to properly evacuate a new one".[11] He wanted to use a tube whose vacuum could be controlled. X-rays are generated at a "high" vacuum, higher than in the usual experiments performed by most others before. The tube he describes in the letter to Warburg can be attached directly to the vacuum pump and therefore the pressure of the vacuum can be adjusted. But the tube described is very different from the usual shape. According to the description, the tube is covered with a

piece of aluminium on the glass opposite the cathode. Roentgen donated such a tube to the Deutsche Museum (German Museum) in 1907, in addition to other tubes he had used in his research. (fig.2) The tube can be seen in a museum cupboard exhibited in those years.[12] (fig 3)

Figure 2 On the right side in the tube you can see the cylindrical anode with the cathode on a stem in the middle. The hole ("window") on the left is closed with a 2 mm thick aluminium plate. At the bottom the pump connection with tap. (from Dörfel, G. , 2010)

Figure 3 The top one, against the left wall, is the "Lenard" tube. Deutsche Museum 1906. (from Hübner, K, 2003)

Roentgen himself also refers to the tube in his Vorläufige Mittheilung (Preliminary Announcement) of December 1895, section 13:

Diese Erzeugung findet nicht nur in Glas statt, sondern, wie ich an einem mit 2 mm starkem Aluminiumblech abgesehlossenen Apparat beobachten konnte, auch in diesem Metall. Andere Substanzen sollen später untersucht werden.[2]

The rays are generated not only in glass. I have obtained them in an apparatus closed by an aluminium plate 2 millimeters thick. Other substances will be investigated later. (translation by author)

Comparison with the Lenard tube

Dörfel et al describe this tube as "Röntgens Lenard-Röhre".[13] They consider the tube to be designed by Lenard and manufactured by the glassblower Müller-Unkel, but the platinum tube at the front is missing and the hole thus created is closed by an aluminium plate. In the Deutsche Museum the tube is described as a "Lenard-Röhre", but Lenard had never conceived such a tube. After visiting the museum in 1924, a year after Roentgen's death, Lenard notes:

Ein Rohr genau wie mein Fensterrohr, aber ohne Pt-Ansatz + ohne meine Fensterwand sondern mit grossen Loch anstelle des Fensters, das mit einem (Al-) Blech verklebt ist.[13]

A tube just like my “window tube” (Fensterröhre), but without Pt attachment + without my “window wall” (Fensterwand), however with a large hole instead of the window, which is glued with an (aluminium) sheet. (*translation by author*)

Another essential difference with the tube that Lenard designed is that the sealing aluminium plate was conductively connected to the anode. That probably caused the tube to have better x-ray output. Lenard had taken explicit measures to prevent the aluminium plate from serving as an anode because of the risk of corrosion. But his aluminium sheet was only 0,00265 mm thick, while Roentgen’s plate was 2 mm. Lenard kept the discharge tube connected to the vacuum pump and used an optimal spark gap of 3 cm. These are almost the same instructions that Roentgen gives in his letter to Warburg, In his 1894 paper, Lenard writes:[6]

Die günstigste Verdünnung ist erreicht, wenn die Potentialdifferenz zwischen den Electroden einer Schlagweite von etwa 3 cm zwischen Kugeln in Luft entspricht [...] Das Entladungsrohr blieb stets an der Pumpe, einer Geissler’schen Quecksilberluftpumpe, denn erhielt sich auch das Vacuum bei unbenutztem Apparate wochenlang unverändert, so stieg doch der Druck während der Benutzung stets merklich an, so dass von Zeit zu Zeit nachgepumpt werden musste.

The best evacuation is achieved when the potential difference between the electrodes corresponds to a spark gap of about 3 cm between spheres [...] The discharge tube always remained on the pump, a Geissler mercury air pump. Since, although the vacuum remained unchanged for weeks when the device was not in use, the pressure always increased noticeably during use, so it was necessary to pump occasionally. (*translation by author*)

Lenard always contested Roentgen's priority. He argued that his tube with the platinum header, which Roentgen ordered from Müller-Unkel a year earlier, was essential for the discovery of the x-rays.[1] As can be seen from this article, Roentgen indeed used the Lenard tube as the prototype, but he adapted it significantly. The philosophy of the design differed in important elements from that of Lenard.

The tube In the Deutsche Museum was destroyed in 1944 by acts of war. Dörfel et al wonder whether it was a modification of the original Lenard tube or whether Roentgen himself had this special tube manufactured by Müller-Unkel. They leave it undecided.[13] The letter from Roentgen to Warburg shows that Roentgen consciously constructed this change.

Whether he used this tube in his presentation to the Emperor cannot be established with certainty, but it seems very likely. The newspaper article about the visit to the Emperor states that Roentgen used a Crookes tube to demonstrate the X-rays. But it is questionable whether the writer of the article could be sure of this, since the tube was packed in a

cardboard casing. Crookes was also a kind of collective name for discharge tubes. It is certain that Roentgen designed a special tube.

Krebs drew another conclusion about the tube Roentgen used. He had advice from a team of experts on the interpretation of the letter to Warburg. He described a Crookes' tube with an aluminium sheet, pasted on the outside of the glass opposite the cathode. (fig. 4)

Figure 4 Krebs proposal (from Krebs, 1973)

The sheet is conductively connected to the anode. But this construction is highly unlikely, both technically and historically. His consulted experts considered it to be a transitional type to the internal platinum anti-cathode tube described by Roentgen in his second article dated March 1896.

However, the sketch that Roentgen made in his February 1896 correspondence with Zehnder is much more suitable as a transition type.[7](fig. 5)

Figure 5 Roentgen's sketch. a. glued brass plate with brazen platinum plate b inclined under 45° . a and b serve as anode. d. aluminium cathode. c. glass tube. (from Roentgen WC and Zehnder, L, 1935)

It may be the same sketch that he urgently sent with his order to Müller-Unkel in the letter of 6 January (though this remains speculation). The model looks like the picture in figure 2, but now includes an internal platinum anode at an angle of 45 to the cathode rays and a hollow cathode of aluminium. It is the archetype of the tube that is used in the following decades. About the same time, others came up with the same construction, such as Walter König (1859-1936) from Frankfurt, Germany.[8] There was such a rapid development that Roentgen himself refrained from making a further contribution to tube constructions.

Conclusion:

A forgotten letter from Roentgen to Emil Warburg reveals that one of the tubes Roentgen used when he discovered the x-rays was the prototype of a Lenard's tube, but with significant alterations. Roentgen probably used this tube to show the X-rays to the Emperor.

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ⁱ Son of Emil Warburg's daughter Lotte Warburg (1884-1948). The letters are still owned by the family and are kept by a great-grandson.